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Seismic imaging of the Portland Hills fault through downtown Portland

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Summary

We acquired 4.7 km of new seismic land streamer data in Portland, Oregon to explore shallow displacements and/or material property changes in strata related to the Portland Hills fault beneath densely populated residential, commercial and industrial areas. Our focus was on the 49 km length of the fault that crosses through downtown corridor. This fault has been previously identified with trench, lidar, well log correlations, and seismic studies. The slip rate on this fault is estimated at 0.2 mm/yr but is generally unknown as the fault characteristics are poorly constrained. We identify offset strata across many profiles and elevated shear wave velocities in the upper 5 m where some faults extend to the land surface. Newly identified faults suggest a broad deformation zone associated with the Portland Hills fault system with minimal displacement on individual faults that may preclude a measurable surface-based expression. This study advances our understanding of earthquake hazards and risks to the Portland, Oregon region.

Regional Setting

Portland, Oregon lies in the Portland Basin, a forearc basin within the Cascadia subduction system. Between the Coast Ranges and the active Cascade volcanic arc, basement consists of Eocene marine rocks, massive Columbia River flood basalts, and localized volcanic and sedimentary deposits (e.g., Madin, 2009). Above basement rocks, fine-grained catastrophic Pleistocene-age (Missoula) flood deposits are mapped. These units consist of poorly defined, massive, to thick beds of silt, fine sand, and clay (Personius et al., 2003). The ~49 km long northwest to southeast trending Portland Hills Fault (PHF) is a potentially active shallow crustal fault that extends beneath downtown Portland and defines the western limit of the Portland Basin. It is considered capable of generating M7 earthquakes, posing significant seismic risks to the Portland metropolitan area.

Seismic approach

We follow the seismic hand streamer approach of Liberty and Otheim (2024) to obtain p-wave reflection imagery in the upper one hundred meters and shear wave velocity (V_s) profiles for the upper five to ten meters for portions of Portland, Oregon where active faulting has been identified, inferred or suspected. We target the fault system that lie beneath residential and commercial districts. Our specific focus was to identify and characterize late Quaternary motion of faults or material property changes that may infer shallow earthquake-related deformation.

Hand streamer data acquisition system

Our seismic hand streamer system consists of forty-eight 40-Hz vertical geophones spaced 0.5 m apart (Figure 1). The geophone elements in our streamer are directly mounted to aluminum plates that are embedded within a fire hose (inset). The fire hose protects the enclosed seismic cable that connects each geophone element. We operate a spring-loaded hammer that is driven by a 12 v, 31.6 Newton-meter 1/8 horsepower electric motor. This source is directly mounted to an electric cart. This hammer imparts a similar ground force to a ~5 kg sledge hammer (50 J). A 1.5 m long rod connects the electric motor and spring assembly to the ground through the center of the electric cart. The hammer is

Figure 1. Seismic hand streamer system designed to image strata in the upper one hundred meters. Photo from Liberty and Otheim (2024).

centered on, and hits a small aluminum plate that is tethered to the bottom of the cart. The plate houses an accelerometer that triggers a two 24-channel Geometrics Geode™ recording system. The hammer, cart and streamer positions are controlled with switches mounted to the cart handle, allowing the operator to move the entire system at discrete intervals with one hand and to trigger the source with the other hand. A laptop computer sits in the cart to allow the operator to view data during data collection.

The cycle time for the hammer is less than two seconds, and the operator can move the cart between source positions every few seconds to acquire data at a rate of a few hundred meters per hour. We include a portable cm-precision global positioning system (GPS) antenna mounted to the cart. We typically operate our source and receiver at 0.5 m spacing to allow for nominal 24-fold reflection data and 0.5 m spaced shear wave velocity (V_s) profiles through Rayleigh wave inversions. We typically record one second records at 0.5 ms sample rate to capture signals up to 700 Hz (anti-aliasing filter). The V_s maps are smoothed over the length of the active geophone spread or 24 meters. Our near offset source to first geophone spacing is dataset dependent. We placed our near geophone either 6 m or 8 m from the source for this

survey. Geophones placed at distances closer to the source are often amplitude clipped or are of low data quality; geophones placed farther from the source typically capture deeper reflectivity without surface wave.

Seismic reflection profiling

We acquire data in a manner similar to marine seismic systems. We generate shots at a fixed location, then source and geophones move in unison. We use a standard seismic reflection processing approach that includes datum statics, velocity analysis, spiking deconvolution, and filtering to produce a stacked image (e.g., Yilmaz, 2001). We use stacking velocities to depth convert the final image (Figure 2). We often observe a center frequency of about 200 Hz for the hand streamer system, with coherent signals at or above 500 Hz, providing meter-scale resolution for seismic layers (Figure 2). Unlike surface wave or first arrival signals, the reflection data quality is typically not influenced by road materials or underlying utilities. For this survey, we replaced our GPS elevation with Lidar measurements to improve elevation corrections for each source and receiver position.

Figure 2. a) Typical seismic shot field gather b) filtered from (a) to remove surface waves and highlight reflectivity. c) semblance velocity analysis showing velocities for select reflectors. d) normal moveout-corrected from seismic data in (b) using velocities obtained from (c). Estimated depths are shown on the right side of the plot.

Shear wave velocity (V_s) profiling derived from Rayleigh waves

We use a standard multichannel analysis of surface wave (MASW) approach to map V_s (e.g., Park et al., 1999 using the fixed source/receiver geometry (Liberty et al., 2021). With this approach, we generate dispersion images for each seismic shot to extract a maximum phase velocity semblance for each frequency (Figure 3). Our Rayleigh wave analysis involves converting each shot gather into the frequency domain through a phase velocity transform (Xia et al., 1999). We use all 48 channels over a 23.5 m

aperture to generate the dispersion images, then we initially auto pick the peak fundamental mode dispersion for a range of frequencies where coherent signals are observed. We generate a phase velocity map at the receiver midpoint for each source position. Where we observe a large step from low to high phase velocity for a given frequency, we assume that higher mode signals represent the peak semblance and we remove these picks prior to V_s inversion. We note that these dispersion images can be generated in near real time during data collection. We typically do not use dispersion values at less than one spatial wavelength, or the streamer aperture divided by the frequency. At these lower frequencies, our uncertainties increase and data quality decreases. For our uncertainties, needed in our inversion, we typically use $\pm 10\%$ of the Rayleigh wave speed for each frequency.

Figure 3. a) seismic shot field gathers along Savier Street (Figure 4). b) Dispersion images, or phase velocity-frequency plots, from shot gathers in (a). c) Peak phase velocity for each frequency for all shot gathers along Savier Street. These data are used to generate V_s profiles shown in Figures 5 through 13.

We use the approach of Lai et al. (2002) to invert the fundamental mode Rayleigh wave signals for each shot gather. We generate our starting model from the observed phase velocities and site characteristics. For example, phase velocities are typically 5 to 10 percent slower than the bulk V_s for that wavelength. Where dry sediments are found, V_p is typically 1.5 to 2.5 times faster than V_s (e.g., Mavko et al., 2020), and soil or rock density can be directly estimated from empirical V_s databases (e.g., Boore, 2016). Where soils are saturated, we typically observe V_p values more than three times the V_s values.

Saturated conditions allow a clear separation of surface waves and reflectivity; thus, data quality for both surface wave and reflection products are improved in the presence of saturated sediments. Although we visually inspect the phase velocity map to ensure only coherent fundamental mode signals are present, our inversion from shot gather to Vs map is mostly an automated process.

Figure 4. Lidar elevation map for the Portland Hills fault. We show inferred USGS (purple line) mapped faults, boreholes that identify top of bedrock (blue circles) from Roe and Madin (2013), and new seismic profile locations (red). We acquired seismic data along 9 seismic profiles.

Seismic Results

Figure 4 shows the location of each seismic profile with elevation and faults as mapped with the Quaternary fault/fold database (<https://www.usgs.gov/programs/earthquake-hazards/faults>).

NW Savier Street profile

The 710 m long west to east Savier Street seismic profile extends from (west of) NW 29th Ave east to NW 25th Ave (Figure 4) with about a 25 m elevation change (Figure 5). This is the northernmost seismic profile where Miocene basalt is mapped immediately west of the profile (Personius et al., 2003) and is identified within a few meters below the surface from nearby drillers logs to the northwest of the profile (Roe and Madin, 2013; https://apps.wrd.state.or.us/apps/gw/gw_info/gw_map/Default.aspx). The Vs profile shows high velocities within the upper few meters for the western 100 m of the profile, consistent with shallow basalt or other cemented (Tertiary-age) units (Figure 5). Vs from the 100 m position (~29th Street) to the eastern extent of the road averages about 200 m/s, consistent with Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits (Personius et al., 2003) and previous VS30 estimates (Roe and Madin, 2013). The highest Vs values are located near position 90 m. The seismic reflection profile shows a prominent (mostly) east-dipping reflector at 10 to 100 m depth (-60 m to 30 m elevation). This reflector is consistent with top of Tertiary (Miocene-age basalt or Troutdale formation). The depth to basalt is listed at 87 m to in the Griffith well, located about 700 m to the northeast of the profile. The lack of reflectivity above basement is consistent with laterally discontinuous overbank and flood deposits. I interpret faults as reflector truncations or diffractions along this primary reflector. Where the PHF is mapped (near position 300 m), small offset faults are identified and bedrock top dip shallows to the east. Additional faults are identified near the western profile termination where Vs is elevated. This suggests that the fault may extend to within a few meters of the land surface. The PHF is identified as a ~250 m wide fault zone with post-Tertiary individual fault displacements upwards of about 10 m and about 100 m of vertical offset across the fault zone. The fault geometry and displacements are similar to the fault zone mapped by Liberty et al (2003).

Figure 5. (top) Average Vs for the upper 5 m for the Savier profile; (middle) Vs profile with depth; (bottom) reflection profile with Tertiary top (red circles) and mapped faults (red dashed line).

NW Kearney Street profile

The 600 m long west to east Kearney Street seismic profile extends from NW 25th Ave east to NW 21st Ave (Figure 4) with about a 20 m elevation change (Figure 6). There were data gaps when crossing 23rd Avenue and 22nd Avenue due to high traffic volume. The profile is located approximately 600 m to the south of the Savier Street profile. The PHF is mapped near the western limit of the profile. Vs for the upper 5 m ranges from 200 to 220 m/s, consistent with Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits (Personius et al., 2003). An elevated Vs zone near 500 m distance matches the location of a mapped fault, but no elevated Vs values are observed near the mapped location of the PHF. The primary reflector is mapped between 40 to 100 m depth. This is consistent with the top of Miocene-age basalt that is identified at 47 m depth at the Good Samaritan Hospital well (200 m south of position 380 m). This reflector varies in elevation and appears to shallow in the center of the profile. I identify 3 faults that span the profile. These faults are based on reflector truncations.

NW Everett Street profile

The 460 m long west to east Everett Street seismic profile extends from NW 24th Ave east to NW 21st Ave (Figure 4) with about a 15 m elevation change (Figure 7). There were data gaps when crossing 23rd Avenue and 22nd Avenue and 21st Avenue. The profile is located approximately 450 m to the south of the Kearney Street profile. The PHF is mapped near the 120 m position. Vs for the upper 5 m ranges from 200 to 300 m/s, consistent with Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits (Personius et al., 2003). Vs is fastest between 50 to 200 m distance. The primary reflector is mapped between 20 to 100 m depth. This is consistent with the top of Miocene-age basalt that is identified at 70 m depth at the UA National Bank well (200 m southeast of position 450 m). This reflector varies in elevation and appears shallowest near the western limits of the profile. I identify 4 faults that are located near the mapped PHF trace. These faults offset bedrock with elevated Vs at the shallowest depths.

SW Main Street profile

The 880 m long west to east Main Street seismic profile extends from NW 12th Ave east to NW 2nd Ave (Figure 4) with about a 20 m elevation change (Figure 8). There were data gaps when crossing most streets due to the high vehicle volume (Sunday morning acquisition minimized this). The PHF is mapped near the 550 m position. Vs for the upper 5 m ranges from 200 to 600 m/s, consistent with Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits (Personius et al., 2003) for the low velocities. Given the significant subsurface infrastructure within the downtown corridor, Vs values may not represent native materials. The primary reflector is mapped between 20 to 100 m depth (best observed on the western half of the profile, consistent with the top of Miocene-age basalt that is identified at multiple well locations (Roe and Madin, 2013). This reflector varies in elevation and appears shallowest near position 700 m. Given the high noise level along this road, it is difficult to definitively map the PHF. However, given the reflector continuity to at least 4th Ave, the PHF may surface farther east than currently mapped.

Waterfront Park bike path

The 580 m long west to east Waterfront Park bike path seismic profile extends along the Willamette River (Figure 4) with about a 4 m elevation change (Figure 9). Vs for the upper 5 m ranges from 180 to 350 m/s, consistent with Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits and fill (Personius et al., 2003). Vs is fastest between 300 to 580 m distance. Here, the Lidar-derived elevations (acquired in 2019) differ from the seismic GPS measurements by upwards of one meter, suggesting fill was added to the subsurface along the southern portions of the profile (confirmed with pre-2019 and 2025 Google Earth imagery). The primary reflector is mapped between 10 to 70 m depth. This is consistent with the top of Miocene-age basalt that is identified at two engineering borings close to the profile. This reflector or reflectors vary in elevation and appears shallowest near the northern portions of the profile. I identify 4 faults that are located near the mapped PHF trace. Given that the faults are mapped at the northern limits of this profile, the PHF zone may extend farther north.

SE Carleton Street profile

The 245 m long west to east Carleton Street seismic profile extends from SE 13th Avenue to SE Milwaukie Avenue (Figure 4) with about a 3 m elevation change (Figure 10). Vs for the upper 10 m ranges from 200 to 300 m/s, consistent with Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits and fill (Personius et al., 2003). Vs is fastest between 120 to 200 m distance. The uppermost reflector is mapped between 10 to 30 m depth, consistent with the top of Miocene-age basalt that is identified in regional water well logs. This

reflector and deeper reflectors shallow near the mapped PHF trace at position 150 m; also consistent with elevated Vs in the upper 10 m. Offset reflectors at positions 75 m and 220 m are consistent with faulting associated with the PHF. The PHF may extend farther east than the profile limit.

SE Rex Street profile

The 360 m long west to east Rex Street seismic profile extends from SE 17th Avenue to SE 22nd Avenue (Figure 4) with about a 11 m elevation change (Figure 11). Vs for the upper 5 m ranges from 300 to 500 m/s, elevated above the mapped Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits and fill (Personius et al., 2003). Vs is fastest between 120 to 200 m distance. The uppermost reflector is mapped between 5 to 20

m depth, consistent with the top of Miocene-age basalt that is identified in regional water well logs. Diffractions between positions 50 to 200 m are consistent with laterally offset bedrock reflectors. The elevated Vs values, coupled with the shallow reflector depths are consistent with shallow bedrock along this profile. Variable road conditions may imply that the elevated Vs along the eastern portion of this profile may be related to buried infrastructure.

Figure 11. (top) Average Vs for the upper 10 m; (middle) Vs profile with depth; (bottom) reflection profile with Tertiary top (red circles) and mapped faults (red dashed line).

SE Nehalem Street profile

The 615 m long west to east Nehalem Street seismic profile extends from SE 18th Avenue to SE 25th Avenue (Figure 4) with about a 12 m elevation change (Figure 12). Vs for the upper 5 m ranges from 200 to 600 m/s, consistent with Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits and fill and shallow bedrock (Personius et al., 2003). Vs is fastest between 200 to 450 m distance. The uppermost reflector is mapped between 10 to 50 m depth, consistent with the top of Miocene-age basalt that is identified in regional water well logs. This reflector and deeper reflectors shallow near the mapped PHF trace at position 300 m; also consistent with elevated Vs in the upper 5 m. Offset reflectors between positions 200 m and 420 m are consistent with faulting associated with the PHF.

Figure 12. (top) Average Vs for the upper 10 m; (bottom) reflection profile with Tertiary top (red circles) and mapped faults (red dashed line).

SE Kuehn Road profile

The 615 m long south to north Kuehn Road seismic profile extends from SE Jola Lane to SE Lake Road (Figure 4) with about a 14 m elevation change (Figure 13). V_s for the upper 5 m ranges from 200 to 250 m/s, consistent with Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits and fill and shallow bedrock (Personius et al., 2003). V_s is fastest near 100 m and 600 m distance. The uppermost reflector is mapped between 10 to 50 m depth, consistent with the top of Miocene-age basalt or cemented gravels that is identified in regional water well logs. The shallow bedrock nature suggests that most of this profile is located on the hanging wall side of the PHF. This is consistent with the seismic profile in Clackamas Park (Liberty et al., 2003). We also acquired an ambient noise horizontal-to-vertical spectral ratio (HVSr) profile at 10 m spacing using three-component 4.5 Hz geophones. Using V_s derived from our active source survey, the two-hour occupations show a single spectral peak that is consistent with top of bedrock depth. The purpose of this study was to show that ambient noise data is a useful tool for bedrock mapping.

Summary

Seismic imaging through Portland has identified the PHF as a distributed fault zone with some evidence for latest Pleistocene motion. Many of the profiles would have benefited from farther extension to the east to capture the full deformation zone. Vs profiles suggest mostly Quaternary, fine-grained surficial deposits and fill along each profile with elevated Vs near mapped faults. Coupled with well log data and field mapping, the PHF remains a high hazard fault beneath a large metropolitan area.

Data Archival

Seismic data are available immediately upon request from liberty@boisestate.edu. Seismic field records will be archived with Earthscope as an assembled dataset.

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